

Comparative voltammetric behaviour of isatin and some of its Schiff bases at a solid electrode

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Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of isatin (1) and its Schiff base, 3-arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-ones (2a-g), has been investigated and compared using cyclic (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) techniques at glassy carbon electrode (GCE) in different solvent systems. CV of isatin (1) solution in DMF in 0.1 M LiCl showed two irreversible reduction step due to successive transfer of two electrons leading to formation of dioxindole whereas Schiff bases in this system gave a single two-electron transfer irreversible reduction peak at all scan rates studied. This is due to high basicity of nitrogen atom of imine bond, proton abstraction and second electron transfer are both rapid. The product was secondary amine in case of Schiff bases. However, in acidic BR buffer, isatin (1) is preprotonated and showed a single irreversible one-electron reduction wave due to formation of its dimer, isatide. Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out to find the number of electrons transferred and products were isolated and identified by spectroscopy. Kinetic parameters i.e. charge transfer coefficient (α_{na}), forward rate constant ($K_{f,h}$), diffusion constant ($D_0^{1/2}$) have also been calculated.

Keywords : Isatin, Schiff base, electro reduction, oxindole, secondary amine.

Introduction

Of the diverse heterocycles, the indole nucleus is well recognized as an important bioactive center for its tuberculostatic, psychotropic, antimicrobial, antidepressive and anti-inflammatory activities¹. Isatin's (indole-2,3-dione) presence in the brain and in other tissues of humans beings is well known but the metabolism of isatin in humans is not yet well elucidated². It has been suggested that tryptophan is converted by intestinal bacteria into indole, which is then absorbed and metabolized in the liver to isatin via 3-hydroxyindole³.

3-Arylimino derivatives (Schiff bases) obtained by the condensation of aromatic amines with isatin are powerful anticonvulsant, antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal agents⁴. Some isatin Schiff bases act as corrosion inhibitors for iron in H₂SO₄ solution⁵. Copper(II) complexes with isatin Schiff base ligands are potential antitumoral agent⁶.

The electrochemical studies of bioactive heterocycles using various electrode systems attained prominence in recent years because electrochemistry is comparable to the redox reactions occurring in the biological systems as both involves heterogeneous charge transfer⁷.

Although there have been numerous studies on the

mechanism of electrochemical reduction of carbonyl compounds in both protic and aprotic solvents⁸, only a few reports are available on electrochemical behaviour of their nitrogen analog, i.e. imines or Schiff bases, out of which most are done in aprotic media⁹. Amines are the main product in electrochemical reduction of amines in protic solvent¹⁰. However, no reports are available on the electrochemical behaviour of imine compounds having heterocyclic moiety attached at one end of the imino group and Schiff bases derived from isatin till date.

In continuation to our earlier work on electrochemical studies on isatin¹¹ and recent findings of isatin's interaction with a wide range of monoamines in biological systems¹², in the present work first a series of Schiff bases of isatin were synthesized with various substituted anilines and secondly their electrochemical behaviour on GCE was studied and compared with isatin mainly : (a) to decide about the rate of electro reduction process; (b) to elucidate the mechanism of electro reduction in different media and (c) to find out the effect of various experimental conditions. Spectral characterization of the products has also been done. Aqueous alkaline medium is chosen for the study of isatin Schiff bases in the present study, as the investigation of electro reduction of imine in aqueous acidic media is difficult, due to its ready hy-

drolisis into parent carbonyl compound.

Experimental

Indole-2,3-dione (isatin) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Schiff base, 3-arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-ones (**2a-g**) were prepared according to literature method¹³. All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}). ¹H NMR spectra were in DMSO-*d*₆ on a Jeol FX 90 Q spectrometer at 89.9 MHz using TMS as internal reference. Purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel plates using benzene : ethyl acetate (3 : 1, v/v) as eluent. Nitrogen analysis was done using Coleman N-Analyzer 29. A Systronics model 106 spectrophotometer was used to record UV-Visible spectra.

The general synthetic approach involves condensation of an equimolar mixture of indole-2,3-dione (0.01 mol) and corresponding aniline (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol in the presence of 2,3-drops of glacial acetic acid for 40–50 min. On cooling, crystals separated out which were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to give yellow needles of 3-arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-ones (**2a-g**) in 75–90% yields (Scheme 1). The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The physical data of synthesized compounds are listed in Table 1. Synthesized compounds were characterized by their IR and ¹H NMR studies. IR of isatin showed bands at 1680 and 1720 cm^{-1} due to 2

>C=O groups and NH band appeared at 3200 cm^{-1} . Formation of 3-arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-one was indicated by the retention of NHC=O absorption band at 1720 cm^{-1} and disappearance of another >C=O absorption of isatin moiety and free primary amino group frequency of aniline in IR spectra at 1680 and 3300–3360 cm^{-1} , respectively. The bands corresponding to C=N appeared at 1620 cm^{-1} and NH of indole moiety at 3250–3150 cm^{-1} . In ¹H NMR spectra characteristic signals were observed at δ 10.93 (singlet, NH of indole), δ 6.76–7.87 (multiplet, 9H, aromatic protons).

A Potentiostat/Galvanostat Model 263A Electrochemical Analyzer (make Princeton Applied Research) was used for recording all voltammograms. The working electrode was a glassy carbon electrode (GCE) with diameter 2 mm; the counter electrode was a platinum wire and reference electrode Ag/AgCl in 3 M NaCl ($E^{\circ} = 0.209$ volts vs NHE).

0.01 M Stock solution of depolariser was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amount in appropriate volume of double distilled water in 30% ethanol or in DMF owing to low solubility of Schiff bases in water. More dilute solutions were prepared by accurate dilution with supporting electrolytes. Supporting electrolytes taken were Universal Britton-Robinson buffer as acidic medium and 0.1 M LiCl solution in DMF as basic medium. All measurements were run in oxygen free environment. Purging and blanketing of nitrogen were done for analyte solution placed in the electrochemical cell of 15 ml capacity for 15 min prior to each experiment. Great care was taken in the electrode pretreatment. Mechanical polishing was done over a velvet micro cloth with a 0.05 α -alumina powder suspension and keeping electrode at initial potential for 60 s before each scan.

Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) was carried out for calculating number of electrons involved in the reduction process. As the products of CPE were known to differ, electrolysis was carried out in a micro cell with a 7 mm diameter graphite electrode as the working elec-

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of synthesized Schiff bases, 3-arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-ones

Compd.	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen (%) Found (Calcd.)
2a	H	210	88	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	12.58 (12.61)
2b	3-CH ₃	235	76	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	11.68 (11.86)
2c	4-CH ₃	222	85	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	11.76 (11.86)
2d	4-OCH ₃	228	86	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.96 (11.11)
2e	4-F	274	83	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OF	11.64 (11.66)
2f	3-Cl	215	86	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	10.49 (10.54)
2g	4-Cl	216	74	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	10.50 (10.54)

R = H (**2a**), 3-CH₃ (**2b**), 4-CH₃ (**2c**), 4-OCH₃ (**2d**), 4-F (**2e**), 3-Cl (**2f**), 4-Cl (**2g**)

Scheme 1

trode, a coiled platinum wire in glass chamber as auxiliary electrode and an Ag/AgCl as reference electrode keeping a blanket of nitrogen over the surface of the solution. The number of electrons was calculated from the plot of amount of charge passed vs $t^{1/2}$.

Results and discussion

Voltammetric studies in aqueous acidic medium : Isatin being a tautomeric substance (Fig. 1) exhibits two chemically dissimilar carbonyl groups, a lactam carbonyl (α) and a keto carbonyl (β). The α -carbonyl group is rendered electro-inactive at least before hydrogen evolution through mesomeric shift with the neighbouring imino group¹⁴. The cyclic voltammogram of isatin (1) in Britton-

Fig. 1. Structures of indole-2,3-dione (isatin).

Robinson buffer at pH 3 is shown in Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammetry results suggest that isatin in aqueous ethanol medium, with BR buffer as supporting electrolyte, is characterized with only one irreversible reduction peak for chosen scan rates from 10 to 100 mV s^{-1} . $E_{p/2}-E_p$ is fairly constant, nearly 55–65 mV, indicating one electron transfer in this pH range¹⁵. The variation of the peak potential with $\log \nu$ (ν : scan rate) is linear and the observed slope is 28.5 mV per unit. $E_{p/2}$ values shift towards more negative potentials with increasing pH, indicating the occurrence of a proton transfer preceding the potential determining electron transfer step. The number of protons (P) involved per molecule of the reactant in the rate-determining step is calculated using following equation¹⁶.

$$P = (dE_{1/2}/dpH) \cdot \alpha n / 0.05916$$

The slope of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH is linear and amounts to 0.058 volts, indicating that one proton is involved in the rate determining step per electron transfer process. The acid-

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 3 mM isatin at GCE in BR buffer at pH 3.0 at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} .

Scheme 2

base equilibrium precedes potential rate determining electron transfer reaction. Rate of protonation is fast leading to formation of isatin dimer, isatide, as main product¹⁷ (Scheme 2).

Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) of isatin is carried out at pH 3.5 in BR buffer at the limiting current of the reduction wave to determine the number of electrons transferred. A plot of $\log I$ vs t plot is linear with slope corresponding to a one-electron transfer. Similar results are obtained when electrolysis is carried out at pH 5. The progress of the electrolysis is monitored by recording UV-Vis spectra at different intervals of time. With the progress of the reaction, absorbance at 387 nm systematically decreases and finally disappears. White crystalline product obtained is identified as mainly dimer, isatide (Scheme 2). Study of Schiff bases in aqueous acidic medium is not feasible due to their hydrolysis to parent carbonyl compounds.

Voltammetric studies in aqueous alkaline medium : 0.1 M solution of LiCl is found to be a suitable supporting electrolyte for electro reduction studies of isatin and its Schiff bases in aqueous acidic media at GCE. Fig. 3 depicts the cyclic voltammograms of isatin (1) and Schiff base (2a) in DMF with 0.1 M LiCl as supporting electrolyte at scan rate 25 mV s⁻¹. Isatin shows two separate

one-electron reduction peaks c_1 , c_2 and one irreversible anodic peak a_1 whereas all Schiff bases under study are characterized with a single two-electron reduction peak, c_1' and one irreversible anodic peak, a_1' (Fig. 3) for chosen scan rates from 10 to 250 mV s⁻¹ in this medium at all concentration range chosen. The linear dependence of peak current on the square root of the sweep rate ($v^{1/2}$) and concentration indicates the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process^{15,16}. $E_{p/2}$ values of reduction wave of both isatin and its imine derivatives shift towards more negative side with increasing scan rate and concentration, also confirming the diffusion-controlled irreversible nature of the electrode process (Table 2). The kinetic parameters, i.e. charge transfer coefficient (αn), the forward rate constant ($K_{f,h}$) and diffusion constant ($D_0^{1/2}$) have been calculated by methods of Meites and Israel¹⁸ (Table 3). Controlled potential electrolysis of 3-arylimino-2H-indol-2-one (2a) was carried out at the plateau potential of the irreversible reduction wave. The value of 'n' was found to be two.

The progress of the electrolysis was monitored using TLC. The product mixture obtained was evaporated to dryness in a rotary evaporator after electrolyses. The solid residue was triturated with diethyl ether several times and the ether soluble portion was subjected to prepara-

Fig. 3. CVs of isatin (1) (.....) and Schiff base (2a) (—) at GCE at scan rate of 25 mV s^{-1} in DMF with aqueous 0.1 M LiCl as supporting electrolyte.

Table 2. Values of cathodic peak potential ($-E_{pc1'}$ /mV) and cathodic peak current ($I_{pc1'}$ /μA) at different concentrations of Schiff bases (2a-g)

Compd.	R	Scan rate (mV s^{-1})	Concentration of Schiff bases (2a-g)							
			1.0×10^{-3}		2.0×10^{-3}		3.0×10^{-3}		4.0×10^{-3}	
			$-E_{pc1'}$ (mV)	$I_{pc1'}$ (μA)	$-E_{pc1'}$ (mV)	$I_{pc1'}$ (μA)	$-E_{pc1'}$ (mV)	$I_{pc1'}$ (μA)	$-E_{pc1'}$ (mV)	$I_{pc1'}$ (μA)
2a	H	20	551	9.62	622.5	12.87	671	17.17	692.3	18.49
		50	554	10.42	627.7	13.93	764.8	18.12	701.9	19.56
		100	557	11.31	630.6	14.86	677.8	19.50	737	20.70
2b	3-CH ₃	20	611.8	2.59	657.4	3.99	681.7	5.20	701.4	6.34
		50	624	3.08	658.2	4.82	680.7	6.28	704.3	8.4
		100	648	3.98	668	6.04	692.5	7.46	719	9.73

Table-2 (contd.)

2c	4-CH ₃	20	692.5	3.01	719	5.73	642.6	8.54	775	10.77
		50	698.4	4.34	727.9	8.25	751	12.59	783.9	14.04
		100	710.2	5.74	739.7	9.49	766.2	16.41	798	18.77
2d	4-OCH ₃	20	701.3	5.45	751.5	6.29	789.8	9.56	828.1	13.07
		50	707.3	7.11	751.8	8.61	792.7	13.31	834	17.87
		100	719	8.89	766.2	13.12	810.4	16.12	848.7	23.9
2e	4-F	20	683.7	8.12	707.3	12.53	733.8	14.54	760	15.92
		50	695	12.27	719	18.88	745.6	20.20	778	24.8
		100	707.3	18.14	733.8	23.9	763	27.80	792.7	33.2
2f	3-Cl	20	725.9	8.64	722	12.09	713	13.56	719	14.14
		50	727.9	10.18	730.9	13.05	722	17.12	734	19.10
		100	745.6	13.42	751.5	20.9	742.6	21.2	758	22
2g	4-Cl	20	727.9	5.29	792.7	10.64	938	15.8	969	16.94
		50	745.6	7.40	795.7	14.09	822.2	17.17	860.5	18.93
		100	766	12.66	807.5	17.52	831	18.04	866.4	19.20

Table 3. Electrochemical characteristics of Schiff bases, 3-arylimino-2H-indol-2-ones (2a-g)

Schiff base no.	R	Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	-E _{pc1'} (mV)	I _{pc1'} (μA)	-E _{pa1'} (mV s ⁻¹)	I _{pa1'} (μA)	Slope (mV)	α _{na}	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ⁻⁵	K _{f,h} × 10 ⁻³
2a	H	20	627.7	13.20	333	1.75	99	0.58	6.22	2.54
		60	648.3	21.00	324.2	3.25	98	0.59	5.72	5.08
		100	657.2	25.3	321.2	3.7	97	0.59	5.31	6.58
2b	3-CH ₃	20	598	5.98	327.1	0.9	91	0.63	2.82	3.57
		60	604	6.84	321	0.95	83	0.69	1.86	8.81
		100	618	8.21	309	1.11	88	0.65	1.72	9.43
2c	4-CH ₃	20	630.6	15.47	347.8	1.38	101	0.57	7.29	2.79
		60	645.4	20.8	330	3.31	100	0.57	5.66	4.82
		100	657.2	25.3	327.1	3.87	102	0.56	5.31	5.81
2d	4-OCH ₃	20	889	8.85	403.7	3.14	135	0.42	4.19	1.31
		60	924	15.59	397.8	3.94	132	0.43	4.24	2.28
		100	933	16.53	389	4.27	126	0.46	3.47	3.48
2e	4-F	20	792.6	16.14	527.5	2.58	103	0.56	7.16	2.6
		60	807.5	23.4	521.6	4.88	98.5	0.58	6.37	4.33
		100	819.3	28.1	512.8	5.78	99.3	0.58	5.90	5.88
2f	3-Cl	20	713	8.23	406	1.8	100	0.58	3.88	2.74
		60	725	13.41	424	2.23	89	0.65	3.65	3.38
		100	742.6	21.2	427	2.59	112	0.51	4.45	4.38
2g	4-Cl	20	845.8	9.47	504	1.67	144	0.40	4.46	1.12
		60	875.2	14.84	501	4.39	149	0.38	4.04	1.85
		100	892.9	18.35	498	5.82	152.8	0.38	3.85	2.28

tive TLC on silica gel plates (Merck) using benzene and ethyl acetate (3 : 1) as the eluent. The eluent was separated and evaporated to dryness. Pale yellow coloured product (3a, m.p. 172 °C) obtained was a secondary amine which was confirmed by IR studies by the disappearance

of absorption band of C=N moiety at 1620 cm⁻¹ and appearance of 3420 due to NH frequency formed by reduction of >C=N linkage to a -CHNH- group. The NHC=O absorption band at 1720 cm⁻¹ and NH of indole moiety at 3250–3150 cm⁻¹ were retained. In ¹H NMR

spectra characteristic signals were observed at δ 10.93–12.48 (2H, hump, NH protons), 4.3 (1H, singlet), 6.76–7.87 (9H, multiplet, aromatic protons). These data indicate that the initial intermediate in the reduction of **2**, and presumably all Schiff bases investigated (**2a-g**), is more reactive than the ketyl formed by reduction of isatin so an electro reduction mechanism for **2** can be proposed as shown in Scheme 3. In case of Schiff bases (**2a-g**), due to higher basicity of the nitrogen species of imine bond, proton abstraction as well as second electron transfer are both rapid and hence a single well developed reduction

wave corresponding to two electron process is observed instead of two separate one electron transfer waves⁸⁻¹⁰.

Differential pulse voltammetry : For Schiff bases **2a-g** at all chosen concentrations, only one two-electron reduction peak is observed between -0.6 to -0.7 volts vs Ag/AgCl, whereas two separate peaks are observed for reduction of isatin in this medium at all selected scan rates. DPV of isatin and imine, **2a** is shown in Fig. 4. Experimental parameter chosen were : potential rang 0.4 V to -1.6 V, pulse amplitude 25 mV, pulse duration 20 ms, step height 2 mV, step time 50 ms, scan rate 40 mV/

Scheme 3

Fig. 4. Comparative DPV study of isatin and Schiff base (**2a**).

s and equilibration time 10 s.

Conclusion :

The present studies indicate that the Schiff bases are reduced to secondary amine in a single step involving two electrons in aqueous LiCl/DMF medium via ECE mechanism. This behaviour contrasts with the two discrete one-electron transfer reduction processes observed for isatin in this medium. The predominant product of the two-electron reduction in case of isatin was found to be dioxindole by conducting controlled potential coulometry. However, system of isatin in aqueous ethanol medium, with BR buffer as supporting electrolyte, is characterized with only one irreversible reduction peak, indicating one electron transfer in this pH range. Product of one electron transfer in this acidic medium is identified as mainly dimer, isatide. Study of Schiff bases in aqueous acidic medium is not feasible due to their hydrolysis to parent carbonyl compounds.

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